

Obesity Modifies the Performance of Fibrosis Biomarkers in Nonalcoholic Fatty Liver Disease

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SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

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SUPPLEMENTARY TABLES

Table S1. Formulae used to derive the composite scores.

Score	Formula
FIB-4 (1)	$\frac{Age \times AST}{Platelets \times \sqrt{ALT}}$
NFS (2)	$-1.675 + (0.037 \times Age) + (0.094 \times BMI) + (1.13 \times IFG/T2DM [1/0]) + (0.99 \times \frac{AST}{ALT}) - (0.013 \times Platelets) - (0.066 \times Albumin)$
APRI (3)	$\frac{AST \div AST ULN}{Platelets} \times 100$
BARD (4)	$(BMI \geq 28 [1/0]) + (\frac{AST}{ALT} \geq 0.8 [2/0]) + (T2DM [1/0])$
HFS (5)	$\frac{1}{1 + \text{EXP}(5.390 - 0.986 \times Age [45 - 64] - 1.719 \times Age [\geq 65] + 0.875 \times Male\ sex - 0.896 \times AST [35 - 69] - 2.126 \times AST [\geq 70] - 0.027 \times Albumin [40 - 44.9] - 0.897 \times Albumin [< 40] - 0.899 \times HOMA [2 - 3.99\ with\ no\ T2DM] - 1.497 \times HOMA [\geq 4\ with\ no\ T2DM] - 2.184 \times T2DM - 0.882 \times Platelets [155 - 219] - 2.233 \times Platelets [< 155])}$
ADAPT (6)	$\text{EXP} \left(\log_{10} \left(\frac{Age \times PROC3}{\sqrt{Platelets}} \right) \right) + (T2DM [1/0])$
FIBC3 (7)	$-5.939 + (0.053 \times Age) + (0.076 \times BMI) + (1.614 \times T2DM [1/0]) - (0.009 \times Platelets) + (0.071 \times PROC3)$
MACK-3 (8)	Online calculator* (AST, Glucose, Insulin, CK-18)

*<http://forge.info.univ-angers.fr/~gh/wstat/mack3-calculator.php> (accessed on 9/14/2021)
 Units: Age, years; AST, U/L; ALT, U/L; Platelets, E10⁹; BMI, kg/m²; Albumin, g/L; PRO-C3, ng/mL.
 IFG, impaired fasting glucose; T2DM, type 2 diabetes mellitus; ULN, upper limit of normal; CK-18, cytokeratin 18.

Table S2. Cut-off values used for the composite scores.

Score	Rule out	Indeterminate result	Rule in
FIB-4 (9,10)	<1.30 (2.0)	1.30 (2.0) – 2.67	>2.67
NFS (2,10)	<-1.455 (0.12)	-1.455 (0.12) – 0.676	>0.676
APRI (11)	≤1	NA	>1
BARD (4)	<2	NA	≥2
HFS (5)	<0.12	0.12 – 0.47	>0.47
ADAPT (6)	≤6.3287	NA	>6.3287
FIBC3 (7)	≤0.4	NA	>0.4
MACK-3 (8)*	≤0.134	0.135 – 0.549	>0.549

*cut-offs are for fibrotic NASH (NASH + NAS≥4 + F≥2).

In parentheses are cut-offs that are used for patients aged ≥65 years.

NA, not applicable.

Table S3. Clinical characteristics of the patients in the Overweight/obese cohort (n=378), stratified by the presence of advanced fibrosis.

	F0–F2	F3–F4
n	350	28
Age, years	49 ± 9	56 ± 9***
Males, n (%)	95 (27)	15 (54)**
BMI, kg/m ²	40.5 [36.4, 44.7]	36.9 [30.5, 43.8]*
Waist circumference, cm	120 [110, 131]	122 [103, 132]
Waist-to-hip ratio	0.94 [0.89, 1.01]	0.98 [0.94, 1.01]*
fP-Glucose, mmol/L	6.0 ± 1.2	7.1 ± 2.1*
B-HbA _{1c} , %	5.9 ± 0.9	6.7 ± 1.2***
fS-Insulin, mU/L	15 ± 11	17 ± 14
HOMA-IR	3.2 [1.8, 4.8]	3.5 [2.0, 8.3]
fP-Total cholesterol, mmol/L	4.3 ± 1.1	4.1 ± 1.3
fP-HDL cholesterol, mmol/L	1.22 ± 0.35	1.16 ± 0.44
fP-LDL cholesterol, mmol/L	2.6 ± 0.9	2.4 ± 1.1
fP-Triglycerides, mmol/L	1.43 ± 1.05	1.73 ± 1.83
P-ALT, U/L	42 ± 35	50 ± 30
P-AST, U/L	33 ± 18	60 ± 36***
P-AST/ALT	0.99 ± 0.75	1.35 ± 0.63***
P-GGT, U/L	45 ± 50	239 ± 303***
P-ALP, U/L	70 ± 30	106 ± 74***
P-Albumin, g/L	39 ± 3	38 ± 8**
B-Platelets, E10 ⁹	256 ± 60	194 ± 62***
Type 2 diabetes, n (%)	138 (39)	23 (82)***
Fibrosis stage (F0/F1/F2/F3/F4), n	204/125/21/0/0	0/0/0/17/11***
NASH, %	12	54***
Direct biomarkers		
PRO-C3, ng/mL	10.8 [8.8, 13.4]	18.8 [12.7, 26.0]***
CK-18 M30 [†] , U/L	164 [119, 249]	312 [243, 440]***
CK-18 M65 [‡] , U/L	209 [151, 341]	506 [235, 677]***
Composite scores		
FIB-4	1.01 [0.77, 1.34]	2.36 [1.66, 3.67]***
NFS [§]	-0.27 [-1.30, 0.54]	0.82 [0.36, 2.01]***
APRI	0.31 [0.24, 0.44]	0.77 [0.42, 1.18]***
BARD	3.0 [1.0, 3.0]	3.5 [2.0, 4.0]*
HFS	0.07 [0.03, 0.21]	0.47 [0.21, 0.63]***
ADAPT	5.01 [4.20, 5.76]	7.60 [6.65, 8.77]***
FIBC3	-1.16 [-2.08, -0.04]	1.04 [0.08, 2.16]***
MACK3 [¶]	0.10 [0.04, 0.22]	0.38 [0.10, 0.67]***

Data are in means ± SD, medians [25th, 75th percentiles], counts (percentages), or percentages. The Mann-Whitney *U* and Chi-squared test were used for statistical testing. **P*<0.05; ***P*<0.01; ****P*<0.001; [†]n=354; [‡]n=361; [§]n=373; ^{||}n=371; [¶]n=352.

f, fasting; P, plasma; S, serum; HDL, high-density lipoprotein; LDL, low-density lipoprotein; ALT, alanine aminotransferase; AST, aspartate aminotransferase; GGT, gamma-glutamyltransferase; ALP, alkaline phosphatase; NASH, non-alcoholic steatohepatitis; NA, not available.

Table S4. Clinical characteristics of the patients in the Swedish cohort (n=646), stratified by the presence of advanced fibrosis.

	F0–F2	F3–F4
n	568	78
Age, years	47 ± 14	56 ± 11***
Males, n (%)	360 (63)	42 (54)
BMI, kg/m ²	27.8 [25.6, 30.4]	29.0 [26.4, 32.2]**
fP-Glucose, mmol/L	5.8 ± 2.0	7.5 ± 3.3***
P-ALT, U/L	80 ± 49	109 ± 65***
P-AST, U/L	46 ± 29	78 ± 50***
P-AST/ALT	0.7 ± 0.7	0.8 ± 0.6***
P-Albumin, g/L	42 ± 4	41 ± 4
B-Platelets, E10 ⁹	252 ± 73	210 ± 62***
Type 2 diabetes, n (%)	69 (12)	24 (31)***
Fibrosis stage (F0/F1/F2/F3/F4), n	163/256/149/0/0	0/0/0/58/20***
Composite scores		
FIB-4	0.90 [0.63, 1.27]	2.06 [1.19, 2.93]***
NFS	-2.46 [-3.33, -1.49]	-0.71 [-1.83, 0.05]***
APRI	0.38 [0.28, 0.56]	0.79 [0.51, 1.36]***
BARD	1.0 [0.0, 1.3]	2.00 [1.0, 3.0]***

Data are in means ± SD, medians [25th, 75th percentiles], counts (percentages), or percentages. The Mann-Whitney *U* and Chi-squared test were used for statistical testing. **P*<0.05; ***P*<0.01; ****P*<0.001; f, fasting; P, plasma; S, serum; HDL, high-density lipoprotein; LDL, low-density lipoprotein; ALT, alanine aminotransferase; AST, aspartate aminotransferase; GGT, gamma-glutamyltransferase; ALP, alkaline phosphatase; NASH, non-alcoholic steatohepatitis; NA, not available.

Table S5. Clinical characteristics of the patients in the Italian cohort (n=213), stratified by the presence of advanced fibrosis.

	F0–F2	F3–F4
n	94	119
Age, years	60 ± 10	63 ± 10*
Males, n (%)	53 (56)	76 (64)
BMI, kg/m ²	29.4 [26.7, 32.9]	29.9 [27.7, 33.2]
fP-Glucose, mmol/L	6.3 ± 1.9	6.8 ± 1.9**
fS-Insulin, mU/L	26 ± 55	30 ± 38
fP-Total cholesterol, mmol/L	5.2 ± 1.3	4.6 ± 3.6***
fP-HDL cholesterol, mmol/L	1.39 ± 0.41	1.27 ± 0.42*
fP-Triglycerides, mmol/L	1.7 ± 0.8	1.6 ± 0.8
P-ALT, U/L	43 ± 26	48 ± 29
P-AST, U/L	34 ± 17	42 ± 19***
P-AST/ALT	0.9 ± 0.3	1.0 ± 0.4*
P-GGT, U/L	56 ± 47	105 ± 120***
P-Albumin, g/L	45 ± 5	43 ± 4***
B-Platelets, E10 ⁹	210 ± 92	158 ± 74***
Type 2 diabetes, n (%)	35 (37)	84 (71)***
Fibrosis stage (F0/F1/F2/F3/F4), n	25/30/39/0/0	0/0/0/40/79***
Composite scores		
FIB-4	1.45 [1.17, 1.95]	2.69 [1.77, 4.24]***
NFS	-0.70 [-1.80, 0.14]	0.48 [-0.31, 1.33]***
APRI	0.36 [0.28, 0.50]	0.60 [0.43, 1.00]***
BARD	2.0 [1.0, 3.0]	3.0 [2.0, 4.0]**

Data are in means ± SD, medians [25th, 75th percentiles], counts (percentages), or percentages. The Mann-Whitney *U* and Chi-squared test were used for statistical testing. **P*<0.05; ***P*<0.01; ****P*<0.001; f, fasting; P, plasma; S, serum; HDL, high-density lipoprotein; LDL, low-density lipoprotein; ALT, alanine aminotransferase; AST, aspartate aminotransferase; GGT, gamma-glutamyltransferase; ALP, alkaline phosphatase; NASH, non-alcoholic steatohepatitis; NA, not available.

Table S6. Clinical characteristics of all patients (n=1237), stratified by the presence of advanced fibrosis.

	F0–F2	F3–F4
n	1012	225
Age, years	49 ± 12	60 ± 11***
Males, n (%)	508 (50)	133 (59)*
BMI, kg/m ²	30.5 [26.7, 37.7]	29.9 [27.3, 33.7]
fP-Glucose, mmol/L	5.9 ± 1.7	7.1 ± 2.5***
P-ALT, U/L	64 ± 47	69 ± 53
P-AST, U/L	41 ± 25	57 ± 39***
P-AST/ALT	0.8 ± 0.7	1.0 ± 0.5***
P-Albumin, g/L	41 ± 4	42 ± 5
B-Platelets, E10 ⁹	250 ± 72	181 ± 73***
Type 2 diabetes, n (%)	242 (24)	131 (58)***
Fibrosis stage (F0/F1/F2/F3/F4), n	394/411/209/0/0	0/0/0/115/110***
Composite scores		
FIB-4	0.97 [0.72, 1.37]	2.30 [1.51, 3.62]***
NFS	-1.59 [-2.79, -0.34]	0.14 [-0.87, 1.12]***
APRI	0.35 [0.26, 0.51]	0.69 [0.47, 1.17]***
BARD	1.0 [1.0, 3.0]	2.0 [2.0, 3.0]***

Data are in means ± SD, medians [25th, 75th percentiles], counts (percentages), or percentages. The Mann-Whitney *U* and Chi-squared test were used for statistical testing. **P*<0.05; ***P*<0.01; ****P*<0.001; f, fasting; P, plasma; S, serum; HDL, high-density lipoprotein; LDL, low-density lipoprotein; ALT, alanine aminotransferase; AST, aspartate aminotransferase; GGT, gamma-glutamyltransferase; ALP, alkaline phosphatase; NASH, non-alcoholic steatohepatitis; NA, not available.

Table S7. Diagnostic performance of the biomarkers and composite scores to identify advanced fibrosis in the Overweight/obese cohort (n=378), stratified by BMI quartiles.

	AUROC (95% CI)	Cut-off	Se	Sp	PPV	NPV
Q1 (n = 95; BMI 32.6 [27.5–34.4] kg/m²)						
ADAPT	0.89 (0.80–0.99)	6.3287	85	84	46	97
FIBC3	0.88 (0.77–0.98)	0.4	46	93	50	92
FIB-4	0.89 (0.80–0.98)	1.30 (2.0)*	85	70	31	97
		2.67	46	99	86	92
NFS (n=93)	0.86 (0.74–0.97)	-1.455 (0.12)*	77	49	20	93
		0.676	46	95	60	92
HFS (n=93)	0.82 (0.68–0.96)	0.12	77	73	31	95
		0.47	54	96	70	93
APRI	0.78 (0.65–0.92)	1	31	96	57	90
BARD	0.59 (0.45–0.72)	2	85	43	19	95
MACK-3 (n=88)	0.67 (0.49–0.85)	0.134	75	55	21	93
		0.549	33	88	31	89
PRO-C3	0.81 (0.67–0.95)	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
CK-18 M65 (n=90)	0.67 (0.52–0.83)	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
CK-18 M30 (n=88)	0.63 (0.48–0.78)	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
Q2 (n = 94; BMI 38.2 [37.3–39.2] kg/m²)						
ADAPT	0.83 (0.66–1.00)	6.3287	60	90	25	98
FIBC3	0.89 (0.79–0.99)	0.4	40	91	20	96
FIB-4	0.83 (0.63–1.00)	1.30 (2.0)*	80	66	9	97
		2.67	20	96	20	96
NFS (n=93)	0.82 (0.63–1.00)	-1.455 (0.12)*	100	25	7	100
		0.676	60	84	18	97
HFS (n=92)	0.94 (0.83–1.00)	0.12	100	71	17	100
		0.47	20	97	25	96
APRI	0.74 (0.49–0.98)	1	40	99	67	97
BARD	0.89 (0.85–0.94)	2	100	19	7	100
MACK-3 (n=90)	0.83 (0.68–0.99)	0.134	75	73	12	98
		0.549	25	97	25	97
PRO-C3	0.60 (0.25–0.96)	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
CK-18 M65 (n=91)	0.86 (0.71–1.00)	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
CK-18 M30 (n=90)	0.90 (0.83–0.98)	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
Q3 (n = 94; BMI 42.3 [41.1–43.4] kg/m²)						
ADAPT	0.99 (0.98–1.00)	6.3287	100	91	27	100
FIBC3	1.00 (1.00–1.00)	0.4	100	86	19	100
FIB-4	0.97 (0.92–1.00)	1.30 (2.0)*	100	77	12	100
		2.67	33	99	50	98
NFS (n=93)	0.80 (0.57–1.00)	-1.455 (0.12)*	100	10	4	100
		0.676	67	79	10	99
HFS (n=93)	0.89 (0.71–1.00)	0.12	100	67	9	100
		0.47	33	98	33	98
APRI	0.95 (0.87–1.00)	1	33	99	50	98
BARD	0.61 (0.31–0.91)	2	100	28	4	100
MACK-3 (n=86)	0.44 (0.00–1.00)	0.134	50	58	3	98
		0.549	0	95	0	98
PRO-C3	0.97 (0.92–1.00)	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
CK-18 M65 (n=88)	0.69 (0.11–1.00)	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
CK-18 M30 (n=86)	0.64 (0.00–1.00)	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
Q4 (n = 95; BMI 48.9 [46.4–51.6] kg/m²)						
ADAPT	0.87 (0.72–1.00)	6.3287	71	84	26	97
FIBC3	0.88 (0.75–1.00)	0.4	86	68	18	98
FIB-4	0.88 (0.72–1.00)	1.30 (2.0)*	86	74	21	98
		2.67	29	100	100	95
NFS (n=94)	0.76 (0.56–0.95)	-1.455 (0.12)*	100	7	8	100
		0.676	86	54	13	98
HFS (n=93)	0.87 (0.73–1.00)	0.12	86	58	14	98
		0.47	71	95	56	98
APRI	0.83 (0.58–1.00)	1	29	99	67	95
BARD	0.69 (0.47–0.90)	2	100	15	9	100
MACK-3 (n=88)	0.72 (0.38–1.00)	0.134	67	60	11	96
		0.549	67	95	50	98
PRO-C3	0.73 (0.46–1.00)	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
CK-18 M65 (n=92)	0.77 (0.54–1.00)	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
CK-18 M30 (n=90)	0.77 (0.50–1.00)	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

*In parentheses are cut-offs that are used for patients aged ≥ 65 years.

Se, sensitivity; Sp, specificity; PPV, positive predictive value; NPV, negative predictive value; NA, not applicable.

Table S8. Diagnostic performance of NFS for advanced fibrosis in the three cohorts, stratified by the presence of type 2 diabetes.

	Overweight/obese cohort (n = 373)		Swedish cohort (n = 646)		Italian cohort (n = 213)	
	Se, % (95% CI)	Sp, % (95% CI)	Se, % (95% CI)	Sp, % (95% CI)	Se, % (95% CI)	Sp, % (95% CI)
Non-T2DM	80 (28–100)	89 (83–93)	65 (51–77)	99 (98–100)	83 (66–94)	97 (88–100)
T2DM	96 (78–100)	61 (53–70)	79 (58–93)	93 (84–98)	97 (92–100)	66 (48–81)

Combined performance metrics for the two cut-offs (-1.455 and 0.676) are shown. Se, sensitivity; Sp, specificity; CI, confidence interval.

Table S9. Diagnostic performance of FIB-4, NFS, APRI, and BARD to identify advanced fibrosis in all patients (N=1237), stratified by BMI categories.

	AUROC (95% CI)	Cut-off	Se	Sp	PPV	NPV
BMI <25.0 kg/m² (n = 160)						
FIB-4	0.88 (0.80-0.95)	1.30 (2.0)*	84	71	41	95
		2.67	52	94	67	89
NFS [†]	0.85 (0.76-0.94)	-1.455 (0.12)*	48	88	50	88
		0.676	19	98	67	83
APRI	0.80 (0.72-0.89)	1.0	36	93	55	86
BARD	0.71 (0.61-0.81)	2	68	65	32	89
BMI 25.0–29.9 kg/m² (n = 442)						
FIB-4	0.81 (0.76-0.87)	1.30 (2.0)*	71	75	40	92
		2.67	43	93	60	87
NFS	0.82 (0.77-0.87)	-1.455 (0.12)*	67	77	40	91
		0.676	31	97	68	86
APRI	0.73 (0.67-0.79)	1.0	32	93	53	85
BARD	0.76 (0.70-0.81)	2	71	71	37	91
BMI 30.0–34.9 kg/m² (n = 265)						
FIB-4	0.86 (0.80-0.91)	1.30 (2.0)*	74	78	52	90
		2.67	42	98	87	84
NFS	0.82 (0.76-0.88)	-1.455 (0.12)*	80	62	41	91
		0.676	40	96	77	83
APRI	0.75 (0.68-0.82)	1.0	32	92	55	81
BARD	0.71 (0.64-0.77)	2	80	62	41	91
BMI 35.0–39.9 kg/m² (n = 159)						
FIB-4	0.86 (0.79-0.92)	1.30 (2.0)*	72	70	35	92
		2.67	24	96	58	85
NFS [‡]	0.78 (0.70-0.86)	-1.455 (0.12)*	93	36	25	96
		0.676	35	87	37	86
APRI	0.79 (0.70-0.89)	1.0	24	98	70	85
BARD	0.64 (0.53-0.75)	2	90	31	22	93
BMI ≥40 kg/m² (n = 211)						
FIB-4	0.92 (0.85-1.00)	1.30 (2.0)*	88	76	23	99
		2.67	44	99	88	96
NFS [§]	0.78 (0.68-0.89)	-1.455 (0.12)*	100	9	8	100
		0.676	75	68	16	97
APRI	0.89 (0.77-1.00)	1.0	31	99	71	95
BARD	0.65 (0.51-0.79)	2	94	22	9	98

*In parentheses are cut-offs that are used for patients aged ≥65 years.

[†]n=158; [‡]n=158; [§]n=209.

Se, sensitivity; Sp, specificity; PPV, positive predictive value; NPV, negative predictive value

Table S10. Separate validation of new BMI-adjusted cut-offs for NFS to identify advanced fibrosis in the three cohorts, compared to the old cut-offs.

Cut-off	Se, % (95% CI)	Sp, % (95% CI)	PPV, % (95% CI)	NPV, % (95% CI)	Indeterminate*, %
Overweight/obese cohort (n = 373)					
-1.455	93 (77–99)	21 (17–26)	9 (6–13)	97 (91–100)	55
0.676	61 (41–79)	78 (73–82)	18 (11–27)	96 (93–98)	
BMI-adj. lower	93 (76–99)	54 (48–59)	14 (9–20)	99 (96–100)	41
BMI-adj. upper	39 (22–59)	94 (91–96)	33 (18–52)	95 (92–97)	
Swedish cohort (n = 646)					
-1.455	69 (58–79)	76 (72–79)	28 (22–35)	95 (92–97)	27
0.676	9 (4–18)	98 (97–99)	41 (18–67)	89 (86–91)	
BMI-adj. lower	73 (62–82)	69 (65–73)	25 (19–31)	95 (92–97)	33
BMI-adj. upper	8 (3–16)	98 (96–99)	30 (12–54)	88 (86–91)	
Italian cohort (n = 213)					
-1.455	93 (87–97)	30 (21–40)	63 (55–70)	78 (61–90)	50
0.676	47 (38–56)	85 (76–92)	80 (69–89)	56 (47–64)	
BMI-adj. lower	91 (84–95)	28 (19–38)	61 (54–69)	70 (53–84)	51
BMI-adj. upper	45 (35–54)	85 (76–92)	79 (67–88)	55 (46–63)	

*Proportion of patients with an indeterminate result (between the upper and lower cut-offs).

Se, sensitivity; Sp, specificity; PPV, positive predictive value; NPV, negative predictive value; CI, confidence interval.

SUPPLEMENTARY FIGURES

Figure S1. ROC curves for the biomarkers to identify (A) advanced fibrosis, (B) significant fibrosis, or (C) fibrotic NASH in the Overweight/obese cohort.

Figure S2. Relationship between BMI and test sensitivity/specificity of (A) HFS, (B) ADAPT, (C) FIBC3, (D) BARD, and (E) APRI to identify advanced fibrosis in the Overweight/obese cohort.

Figure S3. Relationship between BMI and (A) AUROC or (B) sensitivity/specificity of MACK-3 to identify fibrotic NASH in the Overweight/obese cohort.

Figure S4. Relationship between BMI and the AUROCs of NFS, BARD, FIB-4, and APRI to identify advanced fibrosis in all patients (N=1237).

Figure S5. Relationship between BMI and test sensitivity/specificity of (A) FIB-4, (B) BARD, and (C) APRI to identify advanced fibrosis in all patients (N=1237).

Figure S6. Sequential diagnostic algorithm for advanced fibrosis combining FIB-4 and ADAPT in the Overweight/obese cohort.

Figure S7. Sequential diagnostic algorithm for advanced fibrosis combining FIB-4 and FIBC3 in the Overweight/obese cohort.

Figure S8. Sequential diagnostic algorithm for advanced fibrosis combining FIB-4 and HFS in the Overweight/obese cohort.

Figure S9. Sequential diagnostic algorithm for advanced fibrosis combining FIB-4 and NFS in the Overweight/obese cohort.

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